

QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF HOT AIR WELDED E-TEXTILE TRANSMISSION LINES

S. JEVŠNIK¹, F. KALAOĞLU², S. KURSUN BAHADIR²

¹ The University of Maribor, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Maribor, Slovenia

² Istanbul Technical University, Textile Technologies and Design Faculty

simonajevsnik@gmail.com

Abstract:

The manufacturing of electrical circuit using a hot-air welding technology is a very complex task and depends on many parameters. The welding parameters, welding tapes, conductive yarns and fabrics as well as used welding machines should be consistent according to the selected application.

Since the use of hot air welding technology for manufacturing the e-textile transmission lines presents the new issue in the field of textile welding in this study are investigated the influence the welding parameters such as air temperature, welding velocity and pressure between welding wheels on electrical, mechanical and visual appearance properties. In that purpose, the welding air temperature and velocity at selected welding tapes, fabrics and conductive yarns was varied. The estimated quality parameters will give relevant information to the experts for designing the electrical circuits on textiles, the fashion designers for planning new smart garments as well as the manufacturers for developing the new kinds of welding tapes.

Keywords: hot air welding parameters, e-textile transmission lines, quality assessment

1. Introduction

For designing the smart garments by wearable electronics, has to be considered many factors from the concept and purpose of the garment to wearable devices. Wearable devices must look good, besides the aesthetic and comfort of the garment must also reach the end-users requirements.

Nowadays, different textile technologies have been developed to embedded the conductive threads on or into textiles for data transmission. Regards to technological possibilities the e-textile transmission lines can be manufactured by weaving and knitting processes; overprinting or coating the electrical circuit using different conductive materials or polymers, insertion of conductive yarns through sewing or embroidery methods and bonding by thermoplastic tape of the conductive yarn on the fabric surface using different welding technologies [1-6]. The embedding the conductive yarn on fabric by using the welding technologies is a new principle for manufacturing the e-textile transmission lines, although the bonding and welding technologies became widespread in many different application areas in textile nowadays.

Furthermore, hot air welded e-textile transmission lines are designed by fabric, thermoplastic tape and conductive yarn, Figure 1[6].

Figure 1: Hot air welded e-textile transmission line a) schematic and b) real representation [6]

The most used welding or bonding technologies for textiles are hot air and hot wedge welding, ultrasonic, laser and radio frequency welding [7-12]. Typical applications include protective and outdoor garments, underwear, hospital garments, rainwear/outerwear, skiing, snowboarding, cycling, climbing, paddling sports, hiking, industrial worker, tents, footwear, military clothes, hazardous material protective suits etc.

The hot air welding process has a significant influence on all included components of welded e-textile transmission lines. Therefore the welding parameters such as the temperature of the hot air, velocity, pressure and pressure of hot air must be adjust according to the selected fabric, thermoplastic welding tape

and conductive yarn, as well as to the hot air welding machine to reaching the desired quality of manufactured e-textile transmission lines.

Selection of a suitable welding tape and conductive yarn at appropriate hot air welding parameters considering the mechanical properties of base fabric and required properties of welded garment's parts is a significant factor of produced smart garments' quality. The purpose of that investigation is to study the effects caused by welding parameters on the end quality of manufactured e-textile transmission lines during the welding process. At the same time, the gained results will be the base for establishing a the evaluation process for selection proper welding parameters and materials for high quality made e-textile transmission lines via hot air welding technology.

2. Methodology

For manufacturing the e-textile transmission lines were used 100% PES fabric in plain weave suitable for sportswear, two welded band and three types of 100% stainless steel conductive yarns, Table 1. The fabric density in the warp direction was 21,4 picks/cm and in the weft direction 18,4 ends/cm, the thickness was 0,202 mm, and the fabric weight was 163.5g/m². The fineness of the warp and weft yarn was the same in both directions 65,659 tex. The welding tape WT1 was made of three layers (layer 1- warp knitted fabric, layer 2- waterproof film and layer 3- hot melt adhesive), the thickness was 0.355mm, width 20mm, and weight 230.67gm⁻², while tape WT2 was made of two layers (layer 1 - waterproof film and layer 2 - hot melt adhesive film), thickness being 0.163mm, width 23mm, weight 199.78 gm⁻². Both tapes were breathable and waterproof.

Table 1. The properties of the conductive yarns

Code of yarn	Weight (g/m)	Diameter (µm)	Count (dtex)	Yarn twist	Linear resistance (Ω/m)
				(m ⁻¹)	
Y1	0,13	315	90f x 1	149	<70
Y2	0,19	464	90f x 2	207	<35
Y3	0,82	632	275f x 3	224	<12

The welding parameters were adjusted according to used base fabric and endless tapes WT1 and WT2 and recommendation of manufacture of tapes, Table 2.

Table 2. Welding parameters with corresponding codes for selected welding tape

Welding tape WT1				Welding tape WT2				
Temperature / °C	Velocity / m/min	Pressure / bar		Temperature / °C	Velocity / m/min	Pressure / bar		
T1	180	V1	1.5	6.5	T3	280	V1	1.5
	180	V2	3.0		T3	280	V3	2.5
T2	200	V1	1.5		T4	300	V1	1.5
	200	V2	3.0			T4	300	V3

All three conductive yarns with both welding tapes (WT1 and WT2) according to designed work were welded, Table3

Table 3. The designed work plan of welding processes

T1	WT1	V1	P
T2			
T3	WT2		
T4			
T1	WT1	V2	
T2			
T3	WT2		
T4			

The bonding strength of the welded fabric e-textile transmission lines was tested and evaluated according to standard DIN 54310 [12]. A Keithley® multimeter was used to measure the conductivities of the yarns. The linear resistances of yarns were calculated in ohms per meter (Ω/m) by taking measurements along yarn samples' lengths. An Oscilloscope Tektronix ® TDS 2012B) was used to observe the electrical signal waveforms and the recorded signals were analyzed using Matlab ® R2010b software. The SNRs' values were calculated from captured raw data and after that the mean value SNRs of each sample belonging to each conductive yarn were calculated. The formability of welded samples was prepared according to the measurement procedure using FAST measuring system [13]. The visual appearances of welded transmission lines were estimated subjectively. The puckering the surface of the face-side and the visibilities

of the conductive yarns of the welded samples were determined by sample panel developed for that purpose. All the tests were carried out under laboratory conditions (20°C and 65% RH).

3. Results

Figure 2. The influence of welding temperature at constant velocity a) 1.5 m/min and b) 3.0 and 2.5 m/min on bond strength

Figure 3. The influence of welding temperature at constant velocity a) 1.5 m/min and b) 3.0 and 2.5 m/min on linear resistance

Figure 4. The influence of welding temperature at constant velocity a) 1.5 m/min and b) 3.0 and 2.5 m/min on SNR values

Figure 5. The influence of welding temperature at constant velocity a) 1.5 m/min and b) 3.0 and 2.5 m/min on SNR values

Figure 5. Visual appearances of e-textile transmission lines for welding tape WT2, conductive yarns Y1, Y2 and Y3 at welding temperature 180 °C and velocity 1.5 m/min

4. Discussion with conclusions

The bond strength between welding tape and fabric should be carefully adjusted because the conductive yarns must be safely hidden and protected against mechanical and environmental influences. The proper selection of welding parameters is also crucial for obtaining good electro-conductive properties. The results are shown the adequate electrical conductivity properties at certain combinations of welding parameters. Furthermore, for smooth, even and flexible e-textile structure of hot air welded transmission lines besides welding parameters a high attention to the selected fabric, conductive yarn and welding tape should be taken into account.

References

1. Negru D; Buda. CT. Avram D.: Electrical Conductivity of Woven Fabrics Coated with Carbon Black Particles. *Fibres & Textiles in Eastern Europe*, 2012; 1(90):53-56.
2. Kim B.; Koncar V.; Dufour C.: Poly-aniline-Coated PET Conductive Yarns: Study of Electrical, Mechanical and Electro-Mechanical Properties. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 2006; 101(3): 1252–1256.
3. Gasana E.; Westbroek P.; Hakuzimana J.; De Clerck K. Prinotakis G. Kikens P Tseles. D. Electroconductive textile structures through electroless deposition of polypyrrole and copper at polyaramide surfaces. *Surface & Coatings Technology*, 2006; 201: 3547-3551.
4. Vassiliadis S. Electronics and Computing in Textiles. Online access. <http://bookboon.com/en/electronics-and-computing-in-textiles-ebook>. (2012. Access, 15 May 2015).
5. H. H. Kuhn and Child A. D.: Electrically conducting textiles. in Handbook of Conducting Polymers. T. A. Skotheim. R. Eisenbaumer L. and J. R. Reynolds. Eds. New York: Marcel Dekker. 1998. pp. 993–1013.
6. Kurson Bahadir S.; Jevšnik S.; Kalauglo F.: The use of hot air welding technologies for manufacturing e-textile transmission lines. *Fiber and Polymers*, 17, (6), 2015.
7. Violleau E. Ultrasonic welding for composite materials. *Composites magazine* 2014; 87: 92-95.
8. Prabir J. Assembling technologies for functional garments—An overview. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 2011; 36, 380-387.
9. Kah P, Martikainen J. Current trends in welding processes and materials: improve in effectiveness, *Rev. Adv. Mater. Sci.* 2012; 30: 189-201.
10. Shishoo R. The global textile and clothing industry. Woodhead Publishing Series in Textiles, Printed by TJ International Ltd, Padstow, Cornwall, 2012.
11. Jones I.: Joining textiles. Principle and Application. 1st. ed. (G. Stylious Eds), pp.355-373, Woodhead Publishing, Cambridge, 2013.
12. DIN 54310. Testing of textiles; delamination of fusible interlining from upper fabrics, mechanical delamination test, 1997.
13. De Boss A.. "The FAST System for Objective Measurement of Fabric Properties, Operation, Interpretation and Application", CSIRO Division of Wool Technology, Sydney, 1991.

Acknowledgement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 644268. Also, this research work was supported by TUBITAK (The Scientific & Technological Research Council of Turkey) Project no. 214M405 and BİDEB (Science Fellowships & Grant Programs Department), 2221 – Fellowships for Visiting Scientists and Scientists on Sabbatical Leave, for the period 2014-2015.